

A Review of Modern Obturation Techniques

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Abstract

A key theme in the root canal treatment procedure is the proper obturation of the root canal system. Obtaining a hermetic seal is essential for a successful endodontic procedure. The best obturating material for most applications is gutta percha with sealer. However, a major disadvantage is its inability to bond with the root canal dentin. Materials made of bonded resin were created to address this problem. Conventionally, the two fundamental techniques that have been in use for obturation are the lateral condensation and warm vertical compaction techniques. The science and practice of root canal therapy have undergone significant change in the last ten years due to the development of highly improved obturation materials and techniques based on evidence-based protocols. Numerous materials and techniques were created to improvise the root canal obturation. They consist of compaction, injection, heat, vibration, and carrier-based methods. The carrier-based technique using Thermafil is the most promising among the recently improvised techniques.

Introduction

The three-dimensional obturation of the endodontic spaces after they have been thoroughly cleaned, shaped, and disinfected is the ultimate clinical goal of root canal therapy. Obturation, as described by the American Association of Endodontists in 1994, is the process of filling the complete root canal system in three dimensions as near to the cementodentinal junction as feasible.^[1] The primary root canals and all "portals of exit" are sealed during obturation in order to prevent any further exchange of information between the endodontium and periodontium. Therefore, the root canal space must be entirely and permanently filled with the filling in order for there to be no open gaps. It has been demonstrated that inadequate root canal obturation is linked to a number of endodontic failures. The clinician should strive to achieve optimal debridement and shaping of the root canals for effective treatment outcomes. This should be performed using an obturation technique that establishes a three-dimensional seal at the apical, lateral, and coronal levels within the root canal system. Endodontic obturation has advanced to the point where we now understand that the sealer is indispensable for achieving a hermetic seal. Identifying a

sealer that can bond effectively with both the gutta-percha or a comparable core material and the canal wall at the same time has been the challenging aspect. Only if that is achieved we can create a true monobloc.

The preferred obturation method in the past has been the gutta percha point mixed with the sealer. Although gutta percha has a long history of use and is versatile, one disadvantage is that it does not adhere to root canals. Using heat or gutta percha that has been chemically softened, injectable methods, ultrasonics, vibration, and carriers are some of the methods used to obturate root canals. There are materials that use a core carrier around which coating material is wrapped called carrier-based materials. With the introduction of bonded obturation materials, such as methacrylate resins, Clinicians are now able to create an adhesive seal to the root canal dentin even in areas where etching and adhesive agents have not fully penetrated. Additionally, a carrier-based solution for bonded obturation is now accessible and combines a carrier technique with adhesive

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technology.^[2]

History

Prior to 1800, gold was the sole material utilized for root canal fillings. Subsequently, other materials including other metals, zinc oxychloride, paraffin, and amalgam came into use, each with a different degree of success and patient satisfaction. In 1847, Hill developed "Hill's stopping," the first root canal filling material made from gutta-percha^[1]. By 1848, its solution based on mostly bleached GP, quartz and carbonate of lime was available commercially for dental application. Bowman in 1867 reported filling an extracted molar with gutta-percha, as presented in History of Dentistry in Missouri (1938)^[2]. In 1883, Perry made a report about the use of a pointed wire of gold wrapped in soft gutta-percha for obturation^[3]. SS White started producing gutta-percha points in 1887^[4]. Rollins presented a new type of gutta-percha in 1893, containing vermilion. Callahan introduced the employment of rosins by 1914 to dissolve and soften gutta-percha, which would act as a cementing agent^[5]

Rationale of Obturation

The prevention of microorganisms from reaching the periradicular tissues from the oral cavity by ensuring a tight seal is the ultimate goal of obturation. Although it is impossible to achieve a completely impervious or leak-proof seal in practise, every possible measure should be taken to achieve this. A well-protected system's establishment would fulfil three purposes in particular.

- Prevent the entry of microorganisms or substances that could enhance the microbial proliferation into the vacant spaces of the root canal network through coronal leakage.
- Block periodontal or periapical fluids from seeping into the endodontic canal system, which could otherwise sustain bacterial growth.
- Seal off any remaining bacteria to inhibit their survival and potential pathogenic effects following the cleaning and shaping stages of treatment.^[1]

The question of single or multiple visit treatment is brought up by the timing of obturation. Only after thorough chemical and mechanical cleansing of the endodontic canal network may obturation be performed.^[9] If the canal is completely dry and time allows, obturation in the same appointment is recommended. However, if dryness cannot be achieved due to the presence of blood or exudate, placing an inter-appointment dressing is the preferred approach to protect the tooth. While EDTA has been proposed for smear layer removal during canal cleaning, there is no definitive evidence supporting its routine use in endodontic treatment procedure. Nevertheless, it has been demonstrated that its usage in retreatment instances improves the course of treatment.^[12]

Research has demonstrated that root canals lacking an adequate coronal seal are prone to leakage soon after treatment, regardless of the quality of obturation.^[13] This highlights the importance of establishing a proper coronal seal promptly to minimize the risk of coronal leakage. It is well established that therapeutic results can be strongly impacted by the integrity of this seal,^[14] with improved healing rates being demonstrated in teeth with adequate restorations. Cuspal covering restorations are

advised for posterior teeth that have lost their marginal ridges because they increase the likelihood that the tooth will survive by preventing fracture.^[15] To further reduce coronal leakage, the installation of a foundational seal below the core has been advocated.^[16,17] In multi-rooted teeth, the pulp chamber floor and canal orifices should be covered with this sub-seal material.^[16] For this purpose, a number of materials have been suggested, including glass ionomer cement and intermediate restorative material (intermediate restorative material [Dentsply Caulk, Milford, USA]) reinforced with polymethylmethacrylate.

Obturation Techniques

Endodontic obturation can be performed using a variety of procedures. It is crucial to explore different techniques since they each have unique purposes and can produce superior clinical results.

1. Cold lateral compaction

This technique involves pressing gutta-percha cones against the canal walls to ensure complete filling. Its effectiveness is largely due to its simplicity, affordability, and the absence of a need for specialized equipment.^[18] However, some drawbacks include the potential for void formation, inadequate adaptation of the filling material to the canal walls, and incomplete coverage in difficult-to-access areas of the root canal system.^[19]

The procedure requires selecting a master cone that should be positioned roughly 0.5 mm short of the determined working length and is usually one size larger than the master apical file. If the cone does not fit securely at the working length, a larger size should be chosen, or the tip should be trimmed by 1 mm and adjusted for a better fit.^[20] In cold lateral compaction, the master point should exhibit a slight-tug-back and be marginally shorter than the working length.^[21] Once the master point is properly positioned and shows slight resistance to removal, accessory points are added and compacted laterally using a spreader until the canal is completely sealed.^[22]

Variations of lateral compaction techniques are used in cases of curved canals and blunderbuss canals. NiTi spreaders are utilized in curved canals while thermoplasticized gutta percha technology is suited for severely bent canals like dilacerated canals. In blunderbuss canals apexification should be done due to their distinguishable flared out canals. heated gutta percha technique or custom gutta-percha/tailor-made gutta percha are favoured for full obturation of such canals.

Technique for making tailor-made gutta percha: Multiple gutta-percha cones are aligned end-to-end to form a roll, which is then softened using ethyl chloride spray. The outside of the custom-made cone is coated with chloroform, eucalyptus oil, or halothane before being used in the canal.^[23]

2. Warm Lateral Compaction

A simple modification to the cold lateral compaction method includes introducing heat to the gutta-percha. Heating the material makes it more adaptable, allowing for improved condensation and a denser root filling. However, traditional finger spreaders are not efficient at retaining heat for this approach. Instead, specialized heat carriers should be used. These tools are equipped with a blunt plugger tip, which facilitates controlled vertical

compaction of the softened gutta-percha, while the sharp tip facilitates lateral compaction. There are other spreaders that can be heated electrically. It's crucial that the instruments are warmed up very slowly. If the spreader overheats, it may soften the gutta-percha, causing it to get stuck to the instrument and possibly be pulled out of the canal.^[22] The benefits of using this procedure include greater root canal complexity adaption, a decreased risk of void development, and the production of a dense filler.^[24,25]

3. Single Gutta-percha Cone with Sealer

Gutta-percha points with a corresponding taper may be chosen when preparation methods with a greater taper are preferred. Clinicians utilize a single gutta-percha point along with a sealer, as these components provide an optimal fit for the prepared canal. This method's simplicity is its only benefit. The main concern is that most sealers exhibit some degree of solubility. The sealer may eventually be dissolved by tissue fluids because the canal won't be completely filled in three dimensions.^[26] However, in complex anatomical situations, a specially fitting cone can be essential. A slightly bigger cone is chosen, and its apical portion is softened by placing it in hot water or applying solvents like chloroform, rectified turpentine, or eucalyptus oil. The softened cone is then carefully guided to the working length with gentle pressure. After ensuring proper placement, it is marked for orientation, and the process is repeated until the fit is optimal. Once the cone is free from any solvent residues, the canal can be filled using sealer in the standard manner.^[27]

4. The matic Compaction of Gutta-percha

A motorized compactor, essentially a reverse-configured H file, was created by McSpadden in 1979. Gutta-percha becomes plasticized by the compactor's frictional heat, and under pressure, the softened gutta percha is directed into the root canal. A key challenge was maintaining control over the gutta-percha's apical portion, as when softened it could be forced out beyond the apex. To overcome this issue, Tagger introduced a modification to the technique by suggesting the lateral condensation of a master cone along with two or three accessory cones before plasticizing the coronal gutta-percha using a condenser. Extrusion is effectively prevented by sealing the apical portion with lateral compaction of gutta percha.^[28]

5. Vertical Compaction of Warm Gutta-percha

This technique is currently regarded as the gold standard for endodontic obturation. The vertical compaction of warm gutta-percha granules was introduced in 1967 by Schilder. In conditions like C-shaped canals, internal resorption, and canals with webs or fins, it is especially helpful. Although it produced good results, the procedure was time-consuming and challenging to perfect.^[29] The Buchanan technique, which utilizes the System-B heat source to deliver controlled heat to the plugger tip, is widely used today. A non-standard gutta-percha cone is precisely adapted to the canal. A plugger is used to apply a continuous wave of heat to soften and compact the gutta-percha, ensuring a well-condensed filling of the canal in the apical portion. Additional increments may be used to obturate the remaining canal.^[30]

6. Thermoplasticized Injection Techniques

Thermoplasticized injection techniques involve utilizing specialized devices through which heated gutta-percha is compacted into the prepared canal enhancing material adaptability to complex canal anatomies. The commonly used systems include Calamus, Elements, Obtura III, HotShot & Ultrafil 3D.

Obtura III

This technique utilizes a gun with a heating compartment, warming GP upto 160–200 degree celisus. The heated material is injected via a needle (20, 23, or 25-gauge) placed 3-5 mm shy of the working length. Gradual needle withdrawal ensures precise apical filling, which is compacted using pluggers. Incremental filling is employed to achieve optimal sealing.

Limitations: Control over the filling length is challenging, potentially resulting in overextended or underfilled canals. Studies indicate that Obtura II demonstrates better canal wall adaptation compared to other methods.

Ultrafil 3D

The Ultrafil 3D system (Coltène/Whaledent) comprises an injection syringe, a heating unit and 22-gauge stainless steel cannulas. The gutta-percha remains flowable for approximately 45–60 seconds, allowing adequate canal filling.

Calamus

The Calamus system (Dentsply Tulsa Dental Specialties) uses temperature-regulated cartridges with 20 and 23-G needles. Its precise temperature regulation and adjustable flow rates enhance gutta-percha delivery, with specialized pluggers assisting in material compaction.

Elements

The Elements obturation system (SybronEndo) features a handpiece for delivering plasticized gutta-percha, System B heat source, and pluggers. It supports various needle gauges (20, 23, and 25), while Real Seal cartridges utilize 20 and 23-gauge needles for effective obturation.

HotShot

The wireless HotShot system (Discus Dental) is an adaptable tool designed for use with both resilon and gutta-percha. Operating within a temperature range of 150–230°C, it offers needle sizes of 20, 23, and 25-gauge for diverse clinical scenarios.

GuttaFlow

GuttaFlow (Coltène/Whaledent) is a polydimethylsiloxane-based matrix integrated with gutta-percha. It is provided in capsules, offering around 15 minutes working time and setting within 25–30 minutes. While it demonstrates adequate sealing capabilities in some studies, others report inconsistent performance.^[31,33]

7. Coronal back-filling

The terminal 5-7 mm of the root canal can be successfully sealed off using the System-B previously mentioned. The canal is wide enough at that part to accommodate the needle tip of the Obtura. The canal wall is covered with a sealant film. The device is heated to 200°C. To warm the needle, a tiny portion of the heated GP is forced out and then discarded. The needle is swiftly inserted into the canal after that. A void between the two

components of the filling could develop if this part of the protocol is not followed. Once the trigger is activated, the needle is carefully withdrawn while the thermoplasticized GP is dispensed in the root canal. After filling the canal, gutta-percha can be compacted using standard pluggers before being sealed as usual with glass ionomer.^[33]

8. Carrier-based

A carrier coated with GP is used in carrier-based procedures. The carriers were once constructed of stainless steel and titanium. Thermafil, however, is now solely made of plastic Thermafil. A recently developed carrier-based system known as Gutta Core features a crosslinked gutta-percha core. The benefit of this cross-linked GP carrier is that it may be more readily removed in cases of retreatment or post and core. For each of these, the method is the same. The appropriate carrier size is selected using a verifier. It is subsequently warmed for a predetermined period in a specially designed oven to render the outer layer of gutta-percha more pliable. Once heated, the carrier is carefully positioned at the working length within the sealant-coated canal. The coronal GP is then compressed vertically once the carrier's handle has been removed. There are carriers that are compatible with systems like Protaper, Recripoc, Wave one, etc. Although this method saves time, there might be issues with length control and post-operative discomfort.^[34]

9. Continuous Wave Compaction

Interrupted wave compaction and continuous wave compaction techniques are modifications of the warm vertical compaction technique.

The Continuous Wave Compaction Technique

Downpack

- Whether standardized or non-standardized, the master cone should be placed approximately 0.5 mm short of working length until a “tug-back” sensation is achieved. It is essential to maintain canal moisture during this process to promote irrigant movement. This can be facilitated by gently inserting and withdrawing the cone to improve irrigant circulation.
- A System B plunger should be gently inserted into the shaped canal until it slightly binds at a distance of approximately 5 to 7 mm from the working length. Once in place, the position is made by applying a silicone stop.
- Apply a thin layer of sealant to the master cone before applying it to the walls of the root canals. The master cone is then placed.
- The System B heat source should be set to 200°C with a power level of 10 for optimal use. The most user-friendly option is the touch mode.
- Guide the heated plunger steadily through the gutta-percha, stopping 5 to 7 mm short of the working length within three seconds before activating the touch spring.
- Apply consistent apical pressure for a continuous ten-second duration to counteract any shrinkage that may take place as the gutta-percha's apical portion cools.

- The contact spring is again pressed for one full second to ensure proper activation.
- While keeping apical pressure. The plunger was rapidly withdrawn after releasing the switch and pausing for one full second. The excess coronal component of GP should be eliminated as a result.
- After removing the System B plunger, gutta-percha is compacted in the apical region using a Machtou or a Buchanan plunger. Any excess material adhering to the walls of the root canal should be collected and condensed onto the apical mass.^[35]

The down-pack process is executed in multiple stages rather than a single continuous motion in this technique. While it closely resembles the continuous wave method, it incorporates incremental compaction steps for more controlled obturation. Wider canals are advised for this method.

10. Apical Barrier

The preferred choice of material for apical fillings in cases of immature or blunderbuss apices, an appropriate material should be carefully placed and compacted to establish an apical barrier is now calcium silicates. If used properly, these characteristics make them ideal for preventing extrusion. The majority of calcium silicate cements are liquidized powders that must be blended to the desired consistency. The placement of these materials can be aided by a variety of specialized tools, For both orthograde and retrograde applications, systems like the MAP system (Produits Dentaires, Vevey, Switzerland) allow precise material placement at the intended location.^[36] Adding a first dose of calcium hydroxide dressing might provide positive effects in post-procedure using this approach.^[37] When used for obturating a wide root canal or repairing a perforation, calcium silicate cement should be carefully delivered at the designated depth. Unlike conventional materials, it should not be densely compacted but rather gently positioned using a plunger or a broad, flat-ended paper point. This material helps absorb excess moisture within the canal. Additionally, due to the spongy nature of the periradicular tissues, there is no natural resistance form to pack against, necessitating careful placement to ensure an optimal seal. This cement helps absorb excess moisture within the canal. Due to the soft nature of periradicular tissues, which do not provide resistance for compaction, careful placement is crucial. An ideal apical fill should measure 6 mm. For retrograde use, the material can be applied with a carrier or shaped on a Lee block, which forms a thin column that can be easily transferred with an appropriate instrument and accurately positioned in the prepared cavity.^[36]

11. The Hot Modified Obturation Technique

The hot modified obturation technique is a novel approach aimed at enhancing the penetration of bioceramic sealers within the root canal system. Unlike traditional methods, this technique facilitates deeper penetration into lateral canals and dentinal tubules without compromising the properties of the biosealer.

The process begins by positioning the biosealer and gutta-percha cone within the canal, followed by a rapid down-packing procedure at 180°C, maintaining a depth of 6 mm from the working length. This controlled heating ensures the biosealer remains

intact, enabling improved adaptation and sealing of intricate canal structures. Compared to conventional single cone techniques, the hot modified technique demonstrates superior sealing efficiency and filling of complex anatomies, thereby enhancing the potential for greater clinical success.^[38]

Conclusion

Effective obturation is a fundamental step in endodontic therapy, ensuring the sustained effectiveness of root canal therapy. By achieving a three-dimensional seal, obturation prevents microbial invasion, entombs residual bacteria, and protects periradicular tissues from reinfection. Over time, various materials and techniques have been developed to optimize this process, ranging from traditional cold lateral compaction to modern thermoplasticized injection techniques and carrier-based systems.^[39]

Although gutta-percha still remains the most commonly used obturation material, advancements in adhesive sealers and calcium silicate-based materials have improved bonding and biocompatibility. The selection of an obturation technique should depend on the complexity of the endodontic canal network, the clinician's expertise, and the need for long-term clinical success. Moreover, ensuring an adequate coronal seal is just as critical as the obturation itself to prevent reinfection.^[40]

Future innovations in endodontic materials and techniques will likely focus on improving adaptability, durability, and antibacterial properties to enhance treatment outcomes further. Continuous research and clinical advancements will continue to refine obturation strategies, leading to more predictable and successful endodontic therapy.

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